

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH THE SERVICE QUALITY OF SELECTED DINING RESTAURANTS IN TAGAYTAY CITY

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Abstract: Restaurant industry is continuously growing not only locally but internationally. As Filipino people love eating and travelling, restaurants located in different tourist spots became one of the trends today. For the owners of restaurants, customer satisfaction on their quality of service is important. This research explored the customer satisfaction on the service quality of the selected dining restaurants in the city of Tagaytay. The study used quantitative research design and was conducted in five restaurants such as Claw Daddy's, Kenny Rogers, Leslies, Mama Lou's and Mang Jose. There were 100 respondents in the study who were the guests of the restaurants (20 each) in which the researchers distributed questionnaire. The results of the study showed the customers have the highest level of satisfaction on the service quality of the selected restaurants as all the dimensions of service quality such as reliability, assurance, empathy, tangibles, and responsiveness got a weighted mean equivalent to the verbal interpretation of "Excellent". With regards to the significant difference in each demographic profile, this study reveals that there is a significant difference on their perception on the service quality when grouped according to gender in reliability, assurance, and empathy. In terms of age, there is significant difference on the customers' satisfaction specifically in assurance and tangibles. On the other hand, this study also reveals that there is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction to service quality when grouped according to their civil status, occupation, and educational attainment.

Keywords: Service Quality, Restaurants, Customer Satisfaction, Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, Assurance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Casual dining is very popular for families due to its price, appropriateness, and convenience. Customers usually enjoy dining in a full-service restaurant with good atmosphere and quality of services. Food establishments with good tourist attractions usually are the most visited establishments of the customers since they can enjoy the nice view and atmosphere while eating.

In general, the restaurant industry has been continuously growing in the international market. In the United States, restaurant industry contributed to the revenue by the end of 2017 generating 799 billion dollars and generating job opportunities for 10% of the US workforce.

Americans are said to be spending 48% of their food budgets eating outside rather than cooking at home. In Europe, hospitality industry also contributed to the generation of revenue and job opportunities for the people. Consistent growth in restaurant industry took place from 2014 in European countries such as the United Kingdom, France, Netherland, and Germany. On the other hand, in Asia, food service industry has been growing to a rate of almost 10% every year. Because of the continuous changes and trends in the global market, there is a need for the owners of restaurants to adapt and innovate

to survive and compete with other restaurants. Due to the relevance of existing review sites and the emergence of ordering options online with the emergence of the idea of “conscious dining”, restaurateurs need to consider the preferences of the diners. (Cravy, 2018)

Customers in restaurant industry also consider the quality of service being given by the casual dining restaurants aside from the standards and quality of food products, Customers tend to recommend and suggest the restaurant if they are satisfied to the quality of the product and services. (Adriatico, Afalla & Razalan, 2022) The evaluation of service quality is very important on the part of restaurant owners for them to know how to improve and strengthen their capabilities and to boost more profit. (Omar et al., 2016 as cited by (Adriatico, Afalla & Razalan, 2022).

Filipinos love to eat and travel. Therefore, restaurants located near a tourist spot is part of the trend nowadays. They love to visit this kind of restaurants together with their families. To relax from tiring week, they tend to visit and dine during weekends and during holidays. Eating together while enjoying the view may be very relaxing for them. Restaurants located within Tagaytay might be perfect for those people who wanted to eat and enjoy good views since Tagaytay City is one of the favorite places being visited by tourists.

There is a credible online community that has millions of restaurant reviews from all over the world, including locals from every place and tourists and it is called TripAdvisor. Tagaytay is considered as a tourist spot because of several attractions available in the area, nice views, and the weather itself. A place being a tourist spot means there is a need for restaurants for tourist to dine in and since TripAdvisor is an online community with millions of reviews, casual dining restaurants in Tagaytay City is not an exception. The main problems of casual dining restaurants are slow service due to lots of customers, waiting time for food to be delivered in the tables is too long, not so friendly staff as whenever they serve the food, they are not smiling and the way they hold and deliver the plates and other stuff looks like they don't love what they're doing, and they don't care for their customers. Sometimes, the food they are serving is already cold or it gets cold easily because of the cold weather of Tagaytay. They lack staff / manpower to provide the kind of service that they promise and to attend to the needs of every customer. There are also times that the parking space is not enough for customers to park their cars. (TripAdvisor, n.d.)

This study aims to evaluate the quality of service being offered by selected casual dining restaurants located in Tagaytay City as perceived by the customers. This study will help the management of the selected top casual dining restaurants in Tagaytay area to be able to be recognized and compete with other restaurants by assessing the customer satisfaction. This study will also help students that can be future restaurateurs to attain customer satisfaction in their own establishments. It will also help the professors of the Hotel and Restaurant Management to teach their students on how to gain customer satisfaction during their school activities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. DINING RESTAURANTS

In the Philippines, the relevance of casual dining restaurants is also being recognized. In line with this, the Department of Tourism is committed to develop the local restaurants in different tourist spots. They emphasized the need to prioritize food tourism in the country. Among the problems being faced by the local restaurants in the Philippines are limited promotions of their products, the challenges that may result into ineffective delivery of quality ingredients and the lack of knowledge in terms of basics Filipino cuisine. (Arnaldo, 2022)

Every organization or institution must prioritize customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is defined as “the measurement that determines how happy customers are with a company's products, services, and capabilities. Customer satisfaction information, including surveys and ratings, can help a company determine how to best improve or changes its products and services.” (ASQ, 2019)

B. SERVICE QUALITY

A study conducted by Tabuyo et al., (2018) assessed quality of service being given by selected restaurants accredited by Department of Tourism in Tagaytay City. This study chose three restaurants that are often visited by the tourists such as Josephine Restaurant, Concha's Garden Café, and Memory Lane. The study used SERVQUAL to identify the gaps between the expectation of the customers and the service quality being provided by the said restaurants through the five (5) dimensions such as Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy and Responsiveness. The study revealed that in terms of Reliability, the overall evaluation of customers was interpreted as highly influential which suggests that the said restaurants

have a very good operation in terms of accuracy of serving orders, operating hours, and the speed of serving orders. On the other hand, with regards to the Assurance, it was assessed by asking the customers to rate the way how employees serve, the way how the restaurant maintains safety and security and how they control risk. The overall results revealed that the three restaurants provide risk control management and safety environment and make sure that employees are serving foods in a proper way. The result was interpreted with a high result of Highly Influential. In terms of Tangibility, the result of the data revealed that it is Highly Influential as the appearance of the employees wearing their uniform contributes to the positive perception of the customers to the restaurants tangibility. Additionally, the presence of comfortable waiting lounges also contributed to the positive feedback of the diners. With regards to the Empathy, the overall result revealed the interpretation of Highly Influential. Employees welcome the customers in a friendly manner and with a smile while serving them. Lastly, in terms of Responsiveness, it is interpreted as Highly Influential as well as the cleanliness of the area and table is being maintained by the restaurants which leave good impression on their customers. In this study, expectation of customers has a significant relationship with the service quality being offered by restaurants.

A study conducted by Dinero and Apritado (2021) assessed the service quality of restaurants located in Las Piñas City. This study used the SERVQUAL model as a tool to determine the quality of restaurant services. This study used a modified questionnaire from the studies of Nguyen et al. (2018) and Turker et al. (2018). In this study, five dimensions of SERVQUAL were mentioned in the survey which contain different questions that correspond to each dimension. For the tangibles, questions about the physical appearance of dining areas, building exteriors and parking area were asked. This dimension also includes the cleanliness of the restrooms and other facilities and the space of chairs and tables for the customers. This is supported by the study of Mason et al. (2016) stating that physical environment should be maintained and improved always to keep up in the market. Additionally, the study of Dinero and Apritado (2021) mentioned that menu or brochure should be well-designed, and the customers must easily read the content. For the reliability, this study asked the respondents if the restaurants are error-free when it comes to their orders, whether the restaurants are quick in correcting errors and provides services within the promised time. In the study of Kanyal et al. (2016) as cited by Tabuyo et al. (2019), they mentioned that even if the staffs inside the kitchen are working hard to accomplish all orders, slow service can still be present if the staffs who serve the customers are not enough. As stated in the study of Ong et al. (2022), if the services are reliable, it will contribute to the customer satisfaction. For the responsiveness, the respondents were asked to rate speed and quality of services during busy times and the restaurants' commitment to prompt service. The study of Kanyal et al. (2016) as cited by Tabuyo et al. (2019) stated that even if the staffs inside the kitchen are working hard to accomplish all orders, slow service can still be present if the staffs who serve the customers are not enough. Additionally, the study of Ong et al. (2022) provided that the three attributes such as responsiveness, reliability, and assurance, are all part of the training and performance of the staffs. Assurance on the other hand focused on the ability of employees to answer questions of the customers completely, provide comfortable feeling to the customers and the competence and experiences of the employees. The study of Tabuyo et al. (2019) provided that employees need to be trained as it shows that the organization is committed on their advancement and development. Staffs who have confidence can respond to the concerns and questions of the customers. Lastly, empathy was also considered in the survey by asking the respondents to rate how the staffs provide individual attention to its customers and anticipation to the needs and wants of the customers. This also includes if the staffs are putting into their top priority the interests of their customers. This is supported by the study of Tabuyo et al. (2019) as they stated that the eagerness of the employees to attend to the needs and wants of their customers are important in customer satisfaction. Additionally, in the study of Ong et al. (2022), staffs' understanding on the needs of their customers contributes to the customer satisfaction.

C. CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction refers to the positive perception of the customers after consumption of the products and after availing the services being offered by a business or establishment. (Khadka and Maharjan, 2017 as cited by Adriatico, Afalla & Razalan, 2022) A study of customer satisfaction in Dining restaurants revealed that the way how the employees respond to the needs of their customers, the appearance of the restaurant and the price of the food greatly contributed to the satisfaction of the customers. Therefore, this study concluded that for the restaurants to be competitive, the management must put into consideration how the staffs should attend to the needs of the customers, how the physical appearance of the restaurants can be appealing and how they should set justified price for their products. (Adriatico, Afalla & Razalan, 2022)

A study conducted by Wang & Pang (2021) entitled Demographics and Customer Satisfaction concluded that the demographic profile of customers has a significant effect on their satisfaction. People who attained higher education usually have a wider choice and selection of restaurants and don't usually care with the prices if they are enjoying the physical

appearance and quality of the food. With regards to the age, their preferences vary. Gender also has a significant influence on customer satisfaction as the preferences of individuals vary.

A study conducted by Liao (2011) as cited by Wang & Pang (2021) found out the relationship of demographic profile and customer satisfaction on food and beverage consumption behavior. With regards to gender, female respondents tend to be more satisfied with how the employees consider the needs of customers than male. In considering customers' age, the study reveals that the satisfaction of customers as to how the employees dress themselves is higher for those whose age is under 20 than those who belong to the age group 41-50. In education and occupation, the study reveals that there is a significant difference on the level of customer satisfaction on the service quality of restaurants.

D. RELATED LAWS

One of the laws present in the Philippines which is concerned with the restaurant and food industry is Republic Act No. 10611 "Food Safety Act of 2013". This law aims to manage the system of food safety for the purpose of protecting the health of the consumers specifically from "food-borne and water-borne" diseases. This also lays down the responsibilities of Food Business Owners such as ensuring the safety of their products and ensuring that the foods they produce are being prepared according to the standards. It provides the responsibility of food business owners to have enough knowledge on the situations wherein food can become "unsafe and injurious" to the consumers. This Act provided the guide on how to determine whether the food is unsafe for the consumer. This includes the consideration of the "normal conditions of the use of food by the consumer", considering the "normal conditions maintained at each stage of production", considering the "health of plants and animals from where the food is derived". The presence of this law is relevant for the consumers to feel safe in availing the food products being served by the restaurants.

The Code on Sanitation of the Philippines or Presidential Decree 856 provides the sanitary requirements to be complied by food establishments during their operation. They must obtain first the sanitary permit, health certificates and food handlers. It also covers the preservation and quality of food, the use of food serving areas, structural specifications, sanitary facility specifications, vermin control specifications, equipment and utensil specifications, dry storage for non-perishable foods, refrigerated storage for perishable foods, and food servicing operations. This law is important in the service quality of the restaurants as it lays down the specific requirements on the facilities and equipment which can be classified under the Tangible dimension of SERVQUAL. It provides that equipment and utensils being used by the restaurants should be well designed and installed for easy cleaning. This law specifically provided the proper washing of utensils and the need for the sanitary facilities.

FIGURE 1. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework applied in this study. The objective of this study is to determine the level of customer satisfaction on the service quality of selected dining restaurants in Tagaytay City.

FIGURE 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

To achieve the objective of this study, researchers need to determine the dependent variables such as the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Gender, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Occupation, Residence and Frequency of visit and satisfaction of respondents on the service quality of selected dining restaurants. The survey questionnaire is based on the SERVQUAL model. According to Essays, UK (2018), the SERVQUAL model is a popular model applied to quality measurements which researchers commonly used in industries such as hospitality and economy. The SERVQUAL uses five dimensions which include tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, empathy and assurance and which will be the basis of the researchers in constructing the survey questionnaire. This study will determine the level of customer satisfaction on the service quality of selected dining restaurants in Tagaytay City so researchers can come up with proposed strategies to improve their service quality.

This study aims to determine the level of customer satisfaction on the service quality of selected dining restaurants in Tagaytay City. It will specifically answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 Gender

1.2 Age

1.3 Civil Status

1.4 Occupation

1.5 Educational Attainment

1.6 Residence

1.7 Frequency of Visit

2. What is the quality of service of the selected restaurants in terms of:

2.1 Reliability

2.2 Assurance

2.3 Tangibles

2.4 Empathy

2.5 Responsiveness

3. Is there any significant differences between the respondents' level of satisfaction on the quality of service of selected restaurants when the respondents are grouped according to the demographic profile?

4. Based on the findings, what are the recommendations for the restaurant owners to improve their service quality?

III. METHODOLOGY

This presents an outline of research methodology which will be applied in the study. The researchers present the research design for the purpose of this study, the technique to determine the sample size, the instrument to be used and the methodologies to be applied in analyzing the data.

The researchers used Quantitative research for the research method since the data of the proposed study will be interpreted and analyzed numerically. Under the Quantitative research, Descriptive Method is used to describe the customer satisfaction on the quality of service being offered by selected dining restaurants in Tagaytay City.

Tagaytay City is considered as a tourist spot because of the several attractions available in the area, nice sceneries, views, and the weather itself. The researchers chose this area since aside from being one of the popular destinations by tourists, it is in the province of Cavite which will be convenient for the researchers to conduct the study given the limited time and its location.

The official website of Tagaytay City government listed almost one-fifty (150) restaurants located in the City. Out of these 150 restaurants listed, the researchers chose to conduct this study in five (5) selected restaurants. The researchers used the

total population of Tagaytay City as posted by PhilAtlas to come up with the appropriate sample size. This study will distribute the survey questionnaire to twenty (20) respondents in each restaurant.

The researcher used Slovin's formula to come up with an appropriate sample size from the total population of Tagaytay City. (Ellen, 2020) The Slovin's formula is written as:

Where;

n = number of samples

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

N = total population (85, 330)

e = margin of error (0.10)

The respondents were the available customers in the restaurants. In each restaurant, twenty (20) diners from Tagaytay City were asked to answer the survey questionnaire making it a total of one hundred (100) respondents. The customers were given a survey questionnaire which consists of the service quality of the selected dining restaurants. Each customer provided the number of visits in the said restaurant. The researchers chose respondents based on their availability and willingness to participate in this study.

This study used Convenience sampling technique. It is a non-probability sampling method in which respondents are being included in sample size since are the most convenient for the researchers as they can be easily accessed. These respondents are those who are currently within the vicinity of the restaurant during the time of the conduct of the survey and most importantly those who are willing to answer the survey questionnaire.

The researchers adapted and modified the instrument used by Dinero and Apritado (2021) in their study which is also guided by the SERVQUAL model. The researchers conducted a pilot test to validate the reliability of this instrument. Researchers of this current study adapted and modified this survey questionnaire. It was validated by the running statistician, Mr. Mr. Jerome Buhay, their thesis adviser, and the panel. The survey questionnaire was used to determine the customer satisfaction on the service quality of selected top casual dining restaurants in Tagaytay City.

The survey questionnaire used in this study is composed of four (4) parts. First part contains questions that will determine the demographic profile of the respondents. This part would help the researchers to know the gender, age, civil status, occupation, educational attainment, residence, and frequency of visit. Second part of the questionnaire is composed of twenty -five (25) questions that would assess the service quality of Five Dining Restaurants in Tagaytay City based on the perception of the customers. In this part of the survey, the respondents will evaluate the quality of service in five dimensions using the Four-point Likert scale with the value of, excellent, very satisfactory, satisfactory, and poor. Third part contains the five dimensions of SERVQUAL which will be evaluated by the respondents through Four-point Likert Scale. Respondents may write their suggestions and comments for the improvement of restaurants' services at the last part of the survey form.

The researchers utilized online platform to distribute the survey questionnaires. Crowdsourcing was used by the researchers since they used the internet services to gather data from a large and diverse population of respondents. The researchers utilized social media platform to look for willing respondents. Respondents answered the questions by means of the Google Form. They assured the guests and the owners of the restaurants that the information taken will only be for the purpose of this study and the identity of respondents will be considered and treated with outmost confidentiality.

IV. FINDINGS

This presents the results of the data gathered by the researchers. This will answer the statement of the problem.

To answer the first statement of the problem, what is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of (1) gender, (2) age, (3) civil status, (4) occupation, (5) educational attainment, (6) residence and (7) frequency of visit, Tables 1-7 presents the demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. Majority of the respondents are male with the total of 53 (53%) while the total number of female respondents is 47 (47 %). Although, the difference is not that much, it shows that women love to visit the selected restaurants more rather than men.

Table 1: Frequencies of Gender

Levels	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Female	47	47%	47%
Male	53	53%	100%

This is supported by the study of Vespestad and Mehmetoglu (2020) as the study reveals that women are more motivated in learning new cultures and places for mental relaxation.

Table 2, on the other hand presents the demographic profile of respondents in terms of age. Twenty-eight (28%) of the respondents are at age 18-20 while 28 (28%) are 21-25 years old, 19 (19%) are 26-30 years old and 25 (25%) are 31 years old and above. This shown that most of the respondents are in 18-20 and 21-25 years old who are considered as the youngest age group among the respondents. This is maybe due to the reason that younger individuals tend to explore and relax more as part of their nature.

Table 2: Frequencies of Age

Levels	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
18-20 years old	28	28.0 %	41.0 %
21-25 years old	28	28.0 %	43.0 %
26-30 years old	19	19.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by Spence (2002) as cited by Kara and Mkwizu (2020) stating that the desire of an individual to participate in leisure and tourist activities decreases as the individuals get older.

Table 3 presents the frequencies of respondents in terms of civil status. Forty-one (41%) of the respondents are married while 57 (57%) are single and only 2 (2%) belong to other civil status. It means that majority of the respondents are single. Possible that it is due to the reason that people who are not yet married enjoy visiting to destination areas more than married people.

Table 3: Frequencies of Civil Status

Levels	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Married	41	41.0 %	41.0 %
Others	2	2.0 %	43.0 %
Single	57	57.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by the findings of the study of Fan et al. (2015) as cited by Kara and Mkwizu (2020) stating that single people love to discover and learn new things rather than married people, so it is not surprising that in their study, single people were highly motivated to travel. Tagaytay City is known for having a lot of tourist attractions so single people may love to visit some restaurants there.

Table 4 on the other hand presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of occupation. Fifty-one (51%) of the respondents are employed while 33 (33%) are unemployed and 16 (16%) are self-employed. It reveals that most of the respondents are employed as monthly income may influence their decisions to visit restaurants and tourist attractions in Tagaytay City.

Table 4: Frequencies of Occupation

Levels	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Employed	51	51.0 %	51.0 %
Self Employed	16	16.0 %	67.0 %
Unemployed	33	33.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by Ibrahim and Cordes (1993) as cited by Kara and Mkwizu (2020) stating that people who have disposable income may have more desire to participate in leisure and outdoor activities.

Table 5 presents the frequencies of respondents in terms of educational attainment. Forty-three (43%) of the respondents have bachelor's degree, 35 (35%) are in college level, 11 (11%) are high school graduate while 11 (11%) have master's degree. This study reveals that most of the respondents who visit the selected restaurants are college graduate. The possible reason is that these individuals already have the knowledge on the tourist attraction and cultures that they may experience.

Table 5: Frequencies of Educational Attainment

<i>Levels</i>	<i>Counts</i>	<i>% of Total</i>	<i>Cumulative %</i>
Bachelor's Degree	43	43.0 %	43.0 %
College Level	35	35.0 %	78.0 %
High School Graduate	11	11.0 %	89.0 %
Master's Degree	11	11.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by Machingambi & Mhlaga (2016) higher educational attainment increases the desire of individuals to explore and experience more cultures and may also increase their desire to dine in and travel in different places with good tourist attractions like Tagaytay City.

Table 6, on the other hand presents the demographic profile of respondents in terms of residence. Fifty-nine (59%) percent of the respondents live in CALABARZON region, 36 (36%) are in National Capital Region, five (5%) live in another region. This clearly shows that majority of the customers are living in the CALABARZON region which is composed of the provinces located near in Tagaytay City. This is possible due to the reason that people from these provinces may find it more convenient to visit restaurants in Tagaytay City as this is one of the tourist attractions located near to their residences.

Table 6: Frequencies of Residence

<i>Levels</i>	<i>Counts</i>	<i>% of Total</i>	<i>Cumulative %</i>
CALABARZON	59	59.0 %	59.0 %
NCR	36	36.0 %	95.0 %
Others	5	5.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by Kah Lee & Lee (2016) as cited by Zue & Zhang (2020) by stating that the distance of destinations from individuals' residences may influence their desire to travel as it also involves fare expenses and longer travel time.

Table 7 presents the demographic profile of respondents in terms of the frequency of visit. Thirty-one (31%) of the respondents visit the selected restaurants more than once a month, 63 of them (63%) visit once a month while only 6 visits more than once a week. This study reveals that majority of the respondents visit the selected restaurants once a month. This is maybe due to fact that majority of the respondents are already employed which make them busy and therefore have limited time to travel and relax.

Table 7: Frequencies of visits

<i>Levels</i>	<i>Counts</i>	<i>% of Total</i>	<i>Cumulative %</i>
More than once a month	31	31.0 %	31.0 %
More than once a week	6	6.0 %	37.0 %
Once a month	63	63.0 %	100.0 %

This is supported by Ibrahim and Cordes (1993) as cited by Kara and Mkwizu (2020) stating that people who have more free time may have more desire to participate in leisure and outdoor activities.

On the other hand, to answer the second statement of the problem, what is the quality of service of the selected restaurants in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness, the scale to be used for the interpretation of the value of mean are as follows: 1-1.75= Poor, 1.76-2.50= Satisfactory, 2.51-3.25= Very Satisfactory & 3.26-4.00=Excellent. Figures 8-12 present the verbal interpretation of each descriptor in every dimension of service quality.

Table 8: Descriptors for Reliability

<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal interpretation</i>	<i>Ranks</i>
Provides service within the promised time	0.540	3.530	Excellent	1
Provides immediate action in in correcting of wrong services	0.538	3.560	Excellent	3
Provides accurate bill	0.510	3.730	Excellent	5
No error in serving orders	0.544	3.630	Excellent	4
Dependable and consistent	0.626	3.540	Excellent	2
MEAN RELIABILITY	0.438	3.598	Excellent	

For the question if the restaurants provide service within the promised time, the value of the mean is 3.530. For the question if the restaurants provide immediate action in correcting wrong services, the value of the mean is 3.560. On the other hand, the value of the mean for the question if the restaurants provide accurate bill is 3.730. For the “no error in serving orders”, the value of the mean is 3.630 and lastly, 3.540 is the mean value for “dependable and consistent” all of which can be classified as excellent. The computed weighted mean for the reliability is 3.598 which can be interpreted as excellent.

It can be seen that the lowest descriptor in reliability is that the restaurants provide service within the promised time while the one with the highest mean is that the restaurants provide accurate bill. With regards to the lowest descriptor, although it has a verbal interpretation of excellent, possible reason why it has the lowest mean is because there are lots of customers/diners who always dine or order at the restaurants and if will be problematic if there is not enough staffs or employees to serve them within the promised time. It is supported by the study of Kanyal et al. (2016) stating that even if the staffs inside the kitchen are working hard to accomplish all orders, slow service can still be present if the staffs who serve the customers are not enough. For the highest ranked descriptor, it can be due to the reason that employees especially those who prepare the bills see the importance of checking the orders and they were trained to be like that. This indicates a strong ability of the staff in providing reliability correctness. As stated in the study of Ong et al. (2022), if the services are reliable, it will contribute to the customer satisfaction.

Table 9: Descriptors for Assurance

<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal interpretation</i>	<i>Ranks</i>
Employees are capable to respond to the customers' questions correctly and completely.	0.578	3.640	Excellent	4
Staffs make the customers feel confident and comfortable.	0.601	3.610	Excellent	2.5
Customers feel safe.	0.590	3.660	Excellent	3
Employees are competent, well-trained, and experienced.	0.609	3.550	Excellent	1
The restaurant supports the employees.	0.584	3.610	Excellent	2.5
MEAN ASSURANCE	0.523	3.614	Excellent	

For the assurance, the computed weighted mean is 3.614 with the interpretation of excellent. For the question if the employees are capable to respond to the customers' questions correctly and completely, the value of the mean is 3.640, while 3.610 for the question if the staffs make customers feel confident and comfortable both can be interpreted as excellent. With regards to the question if the customers feel safe, the value of the mean is 3.660 with the interpretation of excellent. In terms of the question if the employees are competent, well-trained, and experienced, the value of the mean is 3.550 and lastly 3.610 for the question if the restaurants support the employees both of which can interpreted as excellent.

It can be seen that the lowest descriptor in assurance is that employees are competent, well-trained and experienced while the one with the highest mean is that the employees are capable to respond to the customers' questions correctly and completely. With regards to the lowest descriptor, although it has a verbal interpretation of excellent, possible reason why it has the lowest mean is due to lack of trainings for employees or restaurants tend to hire inexperienced staffs. As supported by the study of Tabuyo et al. (2019), employees need to be trained as it shows that the organization is committed on their

advancement and development. For the highest ranked descriptor, it can be due to the reason that the staffs may have confidence on responding to the concerns and questions of the customers. This is supported by the study of Tabuyo et al. (2019).

Table 10: Descriptors for Tangibles

<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal interpretation</i>	<i>Ranks</i>
Clean, properly maintained, and sanitized restrooms	0.517	3.660	Excellent	2
Visual appealing physical facilities, dining areas, parking areas, and building exteriors	0.490	3.680	Excellent	3.5
Employees are neat-appealing	0.548	3.680	Excellent	3.5
Menu is visually attractive	0.514	3.720	Excellent	4
Provides comfortable dining areas and spacing relative to social distancing	0.624	3.570	Excellent	1
MEAN TANGIBLES	0.445	3.662	Excellent	

On the other hand, for the tangibles, the computed weighted mean is 3.662 which can be interpreted as excellent. The first question if the restaurants have “clean, properly maintained, and sanitized restrooms” the value of the mean is 3.660 while 3.680 for the “visual appealing physical facilities, dining areas, parking areas, and building exteriors” both can be interpreted as excellent. In terms of the question if the employees are neat-appealing, the value of the mean is 3.680 with interpretation of excellent. With regards to the question if menu is visually attractive, the mean value is 3.720 and lastly for the question if the restaurants provide comfortable dining areas and spacing relative to social distancing, the value of the mean is 3.570 both can be interpreted as excellent.

It can be seen that the lowest descriptor in the tangibles is the restaurants provide comfortable dining areas and spacing relative to social distancing while the one with the highest mean is that the menu is visually attractive. With regards to the lowest descriptor although it has a verbal interpretation of excellent, maybe the management doesn't see the importance of managing and improving the physical surroundings. This is supported by the study of Mason et al. (2016) by saying that physical environment should be maintained and improved always to keep up in the market. For the highest ranked descriptor, it can be due to the reason that the management knows how menu will affect customer satisfaction. According to the study of Dinero and Apritado (2021), menu or brochure should be well-designed, and the customers must easily read the content.

Table 11: Descriptors for Empathy

<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal interpretation</i>	<i>Ranks</i>
Give customers individual attention	0.577	3.530	Excellent	2
Employees have anticipation to the customers' needs and wants	0.595	3.510	Excellent	1
Employees give customers special feelings	0.609	3.550	Excellent	3
Employees provide sympathy and reassurance to customers' needs and wants	0.573	3.570	Excellent	4
Employees make sure that the interests of the customers are the top priority	0.597	3.630	Excellent	5
MEAN EMPATHY	0.520	3.558	Excellent	

For the empathy, the computed weighted mean is 3.558 with the interpretation of excellent. For the question if the selected restaurants give customers individual attention, the value of the mean is 3.530 while 3.510 for “Employees have anticipation to the customers’ needs and wants” both of which can be interpreted as excellent. With regards to the question if employees give customers special feelings, the value of the mean is 3.550 with excellent as interpretation. In terms of the question if the employees provide sympathy and reassurance to customers’ needs and wants, 3.570 is the mean value while 3.630 for the question if the employees make sure that the interests of the customers are the top priority both can be interpreted as excellent.

It can be seen that the lowest descriptor in the empathy is that the employees have anticipation to the customers’ needs and wants while the one with the highest mean is employees make sure that the interests of the customers are the top priority. With regards to the lowest descriptor although it has a verbal interpretation of excellent, the possible reason is that employees are not that very much willing and not that attentive when it comes to responding to the needs and wants of their customers. This is supported by the study of Tabuyo et al. (2019) as they stated that the eagerness of the employees to attend to the needs and wants of their customers are important in customer satisfaction. For the highest ranked descriptor, it can be due to the reason that staffs have shown understanding to the needs and feelings of customers. As stated in the study of Ong et al. (2022), staffs’ understanding on the needs of their customers contribute to the customer satisfaction.

Table 12: Descriptors for Responsiveness

<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal interpretation</i>	<i>Ranks</i>
Provides speed in service during busy times.	0.550	3.600	Excellent	2
Employees give quality of service even during busy times	0.570	3.590	Excellent	1
Employees are committed to prompt service	0.549	3.610	Excellent	3
Employees provide extra effort when it comes to responding to the requests of the customers	0.508	3.620	Excellent	4
All employees are responsive to the concerns and requests of the customers.	0.562	3.630	Excellent	5
MEAN RESPONSIVENESS	0.467	3.610	Excellent	

On the other hand, for the responsiveness, the computed weighted mean is 3.610 which can be interpreted as excellent. For the first question if the restaurants provide speed in service during busy times, the value of the mean is 3.600 while 3.590 for the question if employees give quality of service even during busy times both can be interpreted as excellent. In terms of the question if the employees are committed to prompt service, the value of the mean is 3.610 with the interpretation of excellent. With regards to the question if the employees provide extra effort when it comes to responding to the requests of the customers, the mean value is 3.620 and lastly for the question if all employees are responsive to the concerns and requests of the customers, the value of the mean is 3.630 both can be interpreted as excellent.

It can be seen that the lowest descriptor in the responsiveness is that the employees give quality of service even during busy times while the one with the highest mean is all employees are responsive to the concerns and requests of the customers. With regards to the lowest descriptor although it has a verbal interpretation of excellent, the possible reason is that the employees are not enough that’s why they cannot provide quality of service in times when a lot of works await them. This is supported by the study Kanyal et al. (2016) stating that even if the staffs inside the kitchen are working hard to accomplish all orders, slow service can still be present if the staffs who serve the customers are not enough. For the highest ranked descriptor, all employees are responsive to the concerns and requests of the customers, it can be due to the reason that the management provides proper trainings for their staffs. As stated in the study of Ong et al. (2022), the three attributes such as responsiveness, reliability and assurance, are all part of the training and performance of the staffs.

To present the significant differences between the respondents’ level of satisfaction on the quality of service of selected restaurants when the respondents are grouped according to the demographic profile, figures 13-19 are shown. To determine if there is a significant difference on the level of satisfaction when grouped according to the demographic profile, the p value should be less than .05. If the p value is greater than .05, the interpretation is not significant.

Table 13: Gender and Quality of Service

	χ^2	df	p	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	12.227	3	0.007	Significant
Mean Assurance	8.922	3	0.030	Significant
Mean Tangibles	6.415	3	0.093	NS
Mean Empathy	9.283	3	0.026	Significant
Mean Responsiveness	7.298	3	0.063	NS

In Table 13, it can be seen that there is a significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to the gender in terms of reliability, assurance and empathy. On the other hand, with regards to tangibles and responsiveness, there is no significant difference when grouped according to gender.

Table 14: Age and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	5.551	2	0.062	NS
Mean Assurance	15.847	2	<.001	Significant
Mean Tangibles	12.350	2	0.002	Significant
Mean Empathy	5.690	2	0.058	NS
Mean Responsiveness	3.744	2	0.154	NS

In Table 14, it can be seen that there is a significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to the age in terms of assurance and tangibles. On the other hand, with regards to reliability, empathy and responsiveness, there is no significant difference when grouped according to the age.

Table 15: Civil Status and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	0.937	2	0.626	NS
Mean Assurance	0.511	2	0.774	NS
Mean Tangibles	0.757	2	0.685	NS
Mean Empathy	1.149	2	0.563	NS
Mean Responsiveness	2.859	2	0.239	NS

In Table 15, it can be seen that there is no significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to the civil status in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness since p value is greater than .05.

Table 16: Occupation and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	1.918	3	0.590	NS
Mean Assurance	2.644	3	0.450	NS
Mean Tangibles	0.588	3	0.899	NS
Mean Empathy	1.693	3	0.638	NS
Mean Responsiveness	1.568	3	0.667	NS

In Table 16, it can be seen that there is no significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to their occupation in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness since p value is greater than .05.

Table 17: Educational attainment and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	0.581	2	0.748	NS
Mean Assurance	0.303	2	0.860	NS
Mean Tangibles	0.077	2	0.962	NS
Mean Empathy	1.991	2	0.370	NS
Mean Responsiveness	0.336	2	0.845	NS

In Table 17, it can be seen that there is no significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to their educational attainment in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness since p value is greater than .05.

Table 18: Residence and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	8.261	2	0.016	Significant
Mean Assurance	5.839	2	0.054	NS
Mean Tangibles	6.082	2	0.048	Significant
Mean Empathy	5.096	2	0.078	NS
Mean Responsiveness	1.236	2	0.539	NS

In Table 18, it can be seen that there is a significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to their residence in terms of reliability and tangibles. On the other hand, with regards to assurance, empathy and responsiveness, there is no significant difference when grouped according to their residence.

Table 19: Frequency of visits and Quality Service

	χ^2	df	P	Interpretation
Mean Reliability	0.171	2	0.948	NS
Mean Assurance	0.045	2	0.995	NS
Mean Tangibles	0.095	2	0.982	NS
Mean Empathy	1.085	2	0.985	NS
Mean Responsiveness	0.372	2	0.824	NS

In Table 19, it can be seen that there is no significant difference on the respondents' satisfaction on service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to their frequency of visits in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness since p value is greater than .05.

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that for the reliability, since the findings is that the descriptor with the lowest mean is the restaurants provide service within the promised time, the restaurants must hire more staffs especially during the times when there are lots of customers who eat and dine in the restaurants.

For the assurance, the descriptor with the lowest mean is the employees are competent, well-trained, and experienced. The researchers recommend that the managements of restaurants must provide more trainings for their staffs and employees to be more competent in providing the services to the customers.

For the tangibles, the descriptor with the lowest mean is the restaurants provide comfortable dining areas and spacing relative to social distancing. The researchers recommend that the management must focus more on maintaining and improving the physical environment and surroundings of their restaurant as this also affect the customer satisfaction.

For the empathy, the descriptor with the lowest mean is the employees have anticipation to the customers' needs and wants. The researchers recommend that the management must provide incentives or motivations for employees to have the eagerness to be attentive and anticipate the needs and wants of their customers.

For the responsiveness, the employees give quality of service even during busy times has the lowest mean. The researchers recommend that the restaurants must hire additional staffs so they can make sure that quality of service can be provided to everyone even during busy times.

Additionally, since all dimensions of services quality are being seen as "excellent" by the respondents, the restaurant owners must continue improving their service quality to maintain customer satisfaction. They can also conduct surveys for their customers to answer on how they are going to improve their service and must incentivize the customers for them not to hesitate to answer the survey. Incentives can be in the form of free dessert or anything that would motivate them to participate in the survey.

V. CONCLUSION

The study reveals that the respondents have the highest level of satisfaction on the service quality of Claw Daddy's, Kenny Rogers, Leslies, Mama Lou's and Mang Jose in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness.

For the highest ranked descriptor in reliability, that is the restaurants provide accurate bills, it can be due to the reason that employees especially those who prepare the bills see the importance of checking the orders and they were trained to be like that. This indicates a strong ability of the staff in providing reliability correctness.

In terms of assurance, the highest ranked descriptor is the employees are capable to respond to the customers' questions correctly and completely. It can be due to the reason that the staffs may have confidence on responding to the concerns and questions of the customers.

For the tangibles, the menu is visually attractive has the highest mean. It can be due to the reason that the management knows how menu will affect customer satisfaction.

For the empathy, employees make sure that the interests of the customers are the top priority. It can be due to the reason that staffs have shown understanding to the needs and feelings of customers.

And lastly for the responsiveness, all employees are responsive to the concerns and requests of the customers has the highest mean. It can be due to the reason that the management provides proper trainings for their staffs.

On the other hand, when it comes to the significant differences of customers' satisfaction on the service quality of selected restaurants when grouped according to the demographic profile, the researchers concluded that there is a significant difference on their perception on the service quality when grouped according to gender in reliability, assurance, and empathy. In terms of age, there is significant difference on the customers' satisfaction specifically in assurance and tangibles.

This study also reveals that there is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction to service quality when grouped according to their civil status, occupation and educational attainment. Lastly, in terms of their residence, there is a significant difference on their satisfaction when it comes to reliability and tangibles.

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